

First records of myxomycetes from Unalaska Island in the Aleutian Islands

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Abstract: Samples of bark, woody twigs, ground litter, and aerial litter were collected on Unalaska Island in July of 2025 and processed for myxomycetes in moist chamber cultures. Eighty-one percent (55/68) of the moist chamber cultures yielded evidence (plasmodia or fruiting bodies) of myxomycetes. However, only 16 specimens representing six species were recorded. All six are new records for the Aleutian Islands. The vast majority of plasmodia appearing in moist chamber cultures failed to produce fruiting bodies. A few vigorous examples persisted for as long as ten months without fruiting, but most produced sclerotia or simply died off.

Keywords: island biogeography, moist chamber cultures, slime molds, tundra

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Introduction

The myxomycetes are a group of terrestrial amoebozoans that have been reported from virtually every ecosystem examined to date. These organisms mostly occur in association with decaying plant material such as dead wood (from trees and shrubs) and various types of dead plant debris (e.g., dead leaves) on the ground. Myxomycetes produce fruiting bodies that for some species resemble those of certain macrofungi (mushrooms) but are much smaller (usually no more than 1–2 mm tall). Myxomycete fruiting bodies can be collected directly from the field or isolated in moist chamber cultures from samples of various types of plant debris collected in the field and then processed under laboratory conditions using moist chamber cultures (Stephenson and Stempen 1994).

Study area

Unalaska Island (58°38' N, 167°00' W) is a volcanic island in the Fox Island group of the Aleutian Islands and located off the southwestern coast of Alaska. The island has a total area of 545 km², and the highest point is Mount Makushin (elevation 2036 m). Unalaska Island and all the rest of what is now recognized as the state of Alaska belonged to Russia until 1869. The naturally occurring vegetation type on the island is tundra (Fig. 1). The island does not have any naturally occurring trees, but Sitka spruce (*Picea sitchensis*) was planted at one locality by the Russians in 1808, and this species has both persisted

and spread to a limited extent on the island since then. Sitka spruce is a very large tree in its natural habitat but does not get very large (<10 m) on Unalaska Island (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Typical area of tundra on Unalaska Island (Photo by Barbara Stephenson).

Figure 2. Sitka spruce forest on Unalaska Island (Photo by Barbara Stephenson).

Materials and methods

On July 15 and 16 of 2025, samples of woody twigs, ground litter, bark, and aerial litter were collected at several sites on Unalaska Island. These samples were returned to Virginia and used to prepare 68 moist chamber cultures in the manner described by Stephenson and Stempen (1994). Water was added to the moist chamber cultures whenever it became apparent that they were drying out. When fruiting bodies appeared, the portion of the substrate on which they occurred was removed, allowed to dry out, and then mounted in a small pasteboard box for storage. All specimens of myxomycetes were deposited in the personal herbarium (SLS) of the first coauthor.

Results and discussion

Some evidence (plasmodia and/or fruiting bodies) of myxomycetes appeared in eighty-one percent (55/68) of the moist chamber cultures prepared in the present study. However, only 16 specimens representing six species were recorded. The most surprising aspect of the moist chamber cultures was the length of time required for fruiting bodies to appear. The first fruiting body did not appear until after more than two months, and additional specimens appeared at irregular intervals over the next six months. Most of the moist chamber cultures produced vigorous plasmodia that survived for several months or more before producing sclerotia or dying off. Two plasmodia survived for ten months without fruiting before the present study ended.

Annotated List of Species

In the list that follows, all species of myxomycetes recorded on Unalaska Island are arranged alphabetically by genus and then species. Information is provided on the source(s) of each record. The nomenclature used follows Lado (2005-2026).

Arcyria denudata (L.) Wettst.

Represented by three specimens (UI-012, UI-013, and UI-014) appearing on Sitka spruce ground litter (consisting mostly of small twigs) in moist chamber cultures and one specimen (UI-015) appearing on a dead aerial stem of blackberry (*Rubus* sp.) in a moist chamber culture.

Cribraria cancellata (Batsch) Nann.-Bremek.

Represented by one specimen (UI-010) appearing on Sitka spruce ground litter (consisting mostly of small twigs) in a moist chamber culture.

Diderma effusum (Schwein.) Morgan

Represented by two specimens (UI-003 and UI-009) appearing on Sitka spruce ground litter (consisting mostly of small twigs) and one specimen (UI-011) appearing on Sitka spruce bark in moist chamber cultures. *Diderma effusum* and *D. saundersii* are morphologically very similar but can be distinguished by the thickness of the plasmodiocarp (typically 0.4 mm in *D. effusum* and 0.2 mm in *D. saundersii*) and the size of the spores (7–9 μ in *D. effusum* and 10–11 μ in *D. saundersii*).

Diderma saundersii (Berk. & Broome ex Masee) E. Sheld.

Represented by two specimens (UI-001 and UI-002) appearing on Sitka spruce ground litter

(consisting mostly of small twigs) in moist chamber cultures and one specimen (UI-018) appearing on Sitka spruce bark in a moist chamber culture.

Didymium melanospermum (Pers.) T. Macbr.

Represented by one specimen (UI-008) appearing on ground litter from low-growing herbaceous plants in a moist chamber culture.

Metatrachia vesparia (Batsch) Nann.-Bremek. ex G.W. Martin & Alexop.

Represented by three specimens (UI-004, UI-005, and UI-007) appearing on Sitka spruce ground litter (consisting mostly of small woody twigs) in moist chamber cultures and one specimen (UI-006) appearing on a dead aerial stem of blackberry (*Rubus* sp.) in a moist chamber culture.

The percentage of positive moist chamber cultures was relatively high in the present study, but the low number of specimens obtained (only 12) and species recorded (6) were disappointingly low. The only comparable study of which the first coauthor is aware was a study carried out on Macquarie Island in the subantarctic (Stephenson et al. 2007). In the latter study, non-fruiting plasmodia appeared in the majority of moist chamber cultures prepared. Interestingly, Macquarie Island is located at 54°37' S, which is not too different from the location of Unalaska Island at 58°38' N. Whether or not this similarity in latitude (and climate) is a factor of some significance is unknown. In any case, myxomycetes do not appear to be particularly common in tundra. Stephenson and Laursen (1993, 1998) listed only 13 species recorded from areas of tundra in Alaska based on studies carried out during three (1989, 1991, and 1992) field seasons. Only a single species (*Metatrachia vesparia*) reported by these authors also was recorded in the present study.

There are no previous records from the Aleutian Islands, so the six species reported in this paper are new records for both Unalaska Island and the Aleutian Islands. There have been few studies carried out in the tundra ecosystems that occur at higher elevations in the Northern Hemisphere. As such, additional studies are clearly warranted. Hopefully, the present study will serve as a starting point for these studies.

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